

Morphometric Analysis using ALOS-PALSAR radar dataset DEM and Geospatial Techniques of upper Kiul River Basin, Bihar India

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Abstract

Morphometric analysis is an important tool that helps to understand the geological and hydrological characteristics of an area. It helps in sustainable use of the natural resources in a drainage basin. This study is based on upper Kiul River basin in Bihar. It is an important river in south of Ganga River. The study endeavours to explore the drainage basin through different morphometric parameters. To achieve this objective, the study has utilized the “*Advanced Land Observing Satellite-Phased Array Type L-Band Synthetic Aperture Radar (ALOS-PALSAR)*” “Digital elevation model” (DEM) with a spatial resolution of 12.5 meters in ArcGIS 10.3. The linear, areal, and relief characteristics of the basin are taken into consideration. The linear parameter of the basin indicated it as the 6th order basin, with 78% of its streams are 1st and 2nd-order. The mean bifurcation ratio falls within the range of 2-5.6, suggesting that the area is comprised mainly of hilly terrain. The areal aspect of the basin, such as the circulatory ratio, elongation ratio and form factor, indicate that the basin is oval, indicating a moderate level of flash flooding risk and offering information on a number of possible agricultural and dam-building opportunities. From the relief aspect parameters, it is evident that the infiltration rate and groundwater status are low in the upper part, but it increases downward. The findings of the study would help decision-makers to make policies and planning for the sustainable soil & water resource management in the basin.

Keywords: Upper Kiul river basin, Morphometric Analysis, ALOS-PALSAR, Geospatial techniques

1. Introduction

Morphometric analysis is a quantitative approach to understand the form, structure, and development of drainage basins. This method allows analysing the hydrological and Geomorphological behaviour of a watershed (Strahler, 1964; Horton, 1945). Remote sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) play a pivotal role in extracting and analysing morphometric parameters with high precision and efficiency (Shekar & Mathew, 2024).

Morphometric analysis, initiated by Horton (1945) and advanced by Strahler (1957, 1964), evolved from manual methods to GIS- and Remote Sensing-based techniques. Recent years have seen a surge in studies employing these

methods to characterize river basins across varied physiographic settings. High-resolution DEMs, SRTM and ASTER were applied in the Nagar River Basin (Sarkar et al., 2020) and Upper Tons Basin (Yadav et al., 2014). Recent studies using ALOS PALSAR (Ganie et al., 2022; Uddin et al., 2020; Shekar & Mathew, 2024) emphasize watershed prioritization and standardized morphometric assessment frameworks.

Among the various data sources ALOS PALSAR DEM (12.5 m resolution) stands out due to its high vertical accuracy, particularly beneficial in undulating terrains where optical datasets underperform. The radar-based ALOS system is not influenced by cloud cover or vegetation, making it suitable for terrain analysis topographically rugged regions. Ganie et al. (2022) highlighted the effectiveness of ALOS PALSAR in extracting detailed morphometric features in the Saryu River basin, while Kant et al. (2023) emphasized that the fine resolution of ALOS PALSAR enhances identification of micro-watershed boundaries and drainage patterns.

The present study builds upon these recent developments by applying morphometric analysis to a basaltic terrain using ALOS PALSAR DEM integrated with GIS. It aims to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the drainage basin form and function, contributing to flood risk assessment, groundwater recharge planning, and erosion control.

By quantitatively analysing linear, areal, and relief morphometric parameters, this study seeks to deepen the understanding of drainage basin dynamics in semi-arid environments and offers a methodological template for future research across similar physiographic zones.

2. Study Area

The upper Kiul River Basin spans Giridih in Jharkhand and Jamui, Nawada, and Lakhisarai in Bihar. Originating in the Tisri Hills of the Chhotanagpur Plateau, the river flows through Satpahari Hills forming a gorge, enters the plains, and joins the Ganga near Surajgarha. It lies between $24^{\circ}33'40''\text{N}$ – $24^{\circ}52'55''\text{N}$ latitude and $85^{\circ}56'49''\text{E}$ – $86^{\circ}13'55''\text{E}$ longitude (Fig. 1). The region has a semi-arid climate, with peak rainfall during July–September (avg. annual 1300mm) and high temperatures (around 42°C) in May–June.

The Kiul River Basin, divided into Upper (Plateau) and Lower (Plain) regions, lies in the subduction zone of the Indo-Australian and Eurasian plates, influencing its fluvial traits (Yadav et al., 2014). Its geology includes Archaean crystalline rocks, metamorphosed into schist, and features the Chotanagpur gneiss complex (Proterozoic) and Gondwana deposits. Quaternary rocks along drainage channels form soil (Jain et al., 2007). ALOS PALSAR DEM

data show a steeper southern gradient, with elevation ranging from 527m to 21m AMSL. The highest elevation lies along the basin boundary, while the lowest is at the river's outlet point.

Figure 1 Location map of study area

3. Materials and Methods

The topographic maps (in Fig 2) were downloaded (from SOI) and imported into ArcGIS 10.3 software. The dataset was georeferenced and projected using the Projected Coordinate System (PCS) WGS 1984, Zone 45N (Odiji et al., 2021). The topographic map was utilized to improve the spatial accuracy and interpretation of the satellite imagery.

Watershed delineation was performed in ArcGIS 10.3 using ALOS PALSAR 12.5 m DEM (Fig. 3) and the Spatial Analyst extension. The DEM was processed with the Fill tool to remove depressions. Flow Direction and Flow Accumulation raster was generated. A pour point was digitized and snapped to the highest accumulation cell. The

Watershed tool delineated the drainage area, converted it into a polygon for visualization and analysis (Sisay, 2022). Subsequently, morphometric interpretation was carried out based on lithological (Fig. 4) and geomorphological (Fig. 5) frameworks. The respective maps were obtained from the Bhukosh portal and processed using ArcGIS 10.3. These thematic layers are essential for understanding and interpreting the controls on landform development, erosion intensity, and drainage characteristics (Strahler, 1957).

A comprehensive morphometric analysis was carried out to evaluate and compute the Linear, Aerial and Relief parameters (as shown in Fig 7). The calculations were performed using standard geomorphological formulas within a

GIS framework. **Table 1** provides a detailed summary of all the morphometric parameters along with the respective formulae utilized in this study.

Figure 7Flow Chart of Methodology

Table 1Formulae and result for the computation of morphometric criteria

Sl. No.	Morphometric Parameter	Formulas/Definition	Reference	Result
LINEAR PARAMETER				
1	Stream Order	Hierarchical Order	Strahler, (1964)	Refer to table (2)
2	Stream Number(Nu)	No. of stream in each order in a given basin. (Nu=N1+N2+N3.....Nn)	Horton, (1945)	Refer to table (2)
3	Stream Length(Lu)	Total length of streams of particular order. Lu=L1+L2+L3.....Ln	Horton, (1945)	Refer to table (2)
4	Mean stream length(Lsm)	Lsm=Lu/Nu Where, Lsm- Mean stream length Lu- Stream length Nu- Stream number	Strahler, (1964)	Refer to table (2)
5	Stream length ratio(Rl)	Rl=Lu/Lu-1 Where, Rl- stream length ratio Lu- Total stream length of particular order Lu-1- Total stream length of previous order	Horton, (1945)	Refer to table(2)
6	Weighted stream length ratio(Lurwm)	Lurwm= $\sum(Li-Lwi)/Li$ Where, Lurwm-weighted stream length ratio Li-length of each stream segment within the parameter of stream order	Strahler, (1964)	Refer to table(2)

		Lwi-weight assigned to each stream segment		
7	Bifurcation ratio(Rb)	$Rb=(Nu/Nu+1)$ Where, Rb- Bifurcation ratio Nu- Stream order	Horton, (1945)	Refer to table(3)
8	Mean bifurcation ratio (Rbm)	$Rbm=(Nu/Nu+1)/Ns$ Rbm- Mean bifurcation ratio Nu- Stream order Ns- total no. of stream order pair used in summation (n-1)	Strahler, (1957)	Refer to table(3)
9	Weighted bifurcation ratio(Rbwm)	$Rbwm=\sum(Wu*Nu/Nu+1)/\sum Wu$ Rbwm- weighted bifurcation ratio Wu- weighted assigned to the bifurcation ratio between order u and u+1 Nu- stream order		Refer to table(3)
10	Length of main channel (CI)	Using GIS software analysis	Horton, (1945)	74.64
11	Cumulative stream length (Csl)	Using GIS software analysis	Horton, (1932)	1010.1
AERIAL PARAMETER				
1	Basin area (A)	GIS software analysis	Schumm, (1956)	533.4
2	Basin perimeter (P)	GIS software analysis	Schumm, (1956)	168
3	Basin length (Lb)	GIS software analysis	Schumm, (1956)	36.76
4	Mean basin width (Wb)	$Wb=A/Lb$ Where, Wb- Mean basin width A- Basin Area Lb- Basin length	Horton, (1945)	14.510
5	Drainage density(Dd)	$Dd=\sum Lu/A$ Where, Dd- Drainage density Lu- Total length of stream segment of all order A- Area of basin or Grid	Horton, (1945)	1.894
6	Stream Frequency(Fs)	$Fs=\sum Nu/A$ Fs- stream frequency Nu- total number of stream segment of all orders A- Area of river basin or Grid	Horton, (1945)	2.315
7	Drainage texture (T)	$T=Dd*Fs$ Where, T- Drainage texture Dd- Drainage density Fs- Stream frequency	Horton, (1932)	7.3512
8	Drainage intensity (Di)	$Di=Fs/Dd$ Where, Di- Drainage intensity Fs- Stream frequency Dd- Drainage density	Faniran, (1968)	1.222
9	Drainage texture ratio (Rt)	$Rt=Nu/P$ Where, Rt- Drainage texture ratio Nu- total number of streams of all	Horton, (1945)	7.351

		orders P- Perimeter of basin		
10	Infiltration number (If)	If=Rt*Fs If- Infiltration number Rt- Drainage texture ratio Fs- Stream frequency	Horton, (1945)	17.018
11	Length of overland flow (Lg)	$Lg=1/2Dd$ Where, Lg- Length of overland flow Dd- Drainage density	Horton, (1945)	0.528
12	Constant of channel maintenance	$C=1/Dd$ Where, C- Constant of channel maintenance Dd- Drainage density	Schumm, (1956)	0.264
13	Elongated ratio (Re)	$Re=D/L=1.128A^{0.5}/L$ Where, Re- Elongated ratio D- Diameter of circle of the same area A- Basin area L- Basin length	Schumm, (1956)	0.708
14	Circulatory ratio (Rc)	$Rc=4\pi*A/P^2$ Where, Rc- Circulatory ratio A- Basin area P- Basin perimeter	Miller, (1953)	0.238
15	Shape factor (Bs)	$Bs=L^2/A$ Bs- shape factor L- Length of the basin A- Basin area	Horton, (1932)	2.534
16	Compactness coefficient (Cc)	$Cc= P/2(\pi*A)^{0.5}$	Gravelius, (1914)	2.052
17	Fitness Ratio (Rf)	$Rf= CI/P$ Where, Rf- Fitness ratio CI- Length of main channel P- Basin perimeter	Melton, (1957)	0.444
18	Sinuosity index	$Si=CL/VL$ Where, CL- length of main channel VL- Straight-line Distance between Start and End Points		2.03
19	Lemniscate (K)	$K=L^2/4A$ Where, K- Lemniscate Lb- Length of the basin A- Basin area	Chorley et al., (1957)	2.611
20	Form factor (Ff)	$Ff=A/L^2$ Where, Ff- Form factor A- Basin area L- Length of the stream	Horton, (1945)	0.096
21	Rho coefficient (p)	$P=Lur/Rb$ Where, p- Rho coefficient Lur- Stream length ratio	Horton, (1945)	0.578

		Rb- Bifurcation ratio		
22	Shape index (Sw)	Sw=1/Fs Where, Sw- Shape index Fs- stream frequency	Horton, (1932)	0.432
RELIEF PARAMETER				
1	Maximum height of the basin (H)	GIS software analysis		527
2	Minimum height of the basin (H)	GIS software analysis		21
3	Basin relief	R=H-h Where, R- Basin relief H- Maximum height of the basin h- minimum height of the basin	Schumm, (1961)	506
4	Relief ratio (Rr)	Rr=R/L Where, Rr- Relief ratio R- Basin relief L- Longest axis of major river	Schumm, (1961)	0.0138
5	Relative relief (Rhp)	Rhp=R/P*100 Where, Rhp- Relative relief R- Basin relief P- Perimeter	Melton, (1957)	3.012
6	Ruggedness number (Rn)	Rn=Dd*(H/1000) Where, Rn- ruggedness number Dd- Drainage density H- Maximum height of the basin	Patton & Baker, (1976)	0.9584
7	Melton ruggedness number (MRn)	MRn=R/A ^{0.5} Where, MRn- Melton ruggedness number R- Basin relief A- Basin area	Melton, (1965)	21.914
8	Dissection index (DI)	DI= R/Ra Where, Dis- Dissection index R- Basin relief Ra- Absolute relief	Singh & dubey, (1994)	0.477
9	Absolute relief (Ra)	GIS software analysis		
10	Gradient ratio (Rg)	Rg=(H-h)/Lb Where, Rg- Gradient ratio H- Maximum height of the basin h- Minimum height of the basin Lb- Length of the basin	Sreedevi, (2004)	6.78m/km
11	Slope analysis	GIS software analysis	----	---
12	Asymmetry Factor(AF)	AF=100(Ar/At) Where, AF- asymmetry factor Ar-Area of the drainage basin to the right of the main stream At- Total area of the drainage basin	Molin et al., (2004)	57%
13	Total contour length (Ctl)	GIS software analysis		1179.06km

14	Contour interval (Cin)	GIS software analysis	----	50m
15	Mean slope of overall basin (Os)	$Os = (Ct_l * C_{in}) / A$ Where, Os- Mean slope of overall basin Ct _l - Total contour length C _{in} - Contour interval A- Basin area	Chorley et al., (1957)	0.110
16	Hypsometric integral (HI)	$HI = 2 * \text{Area under the curve} / (\text{Basin area} * \text{Total elevation range})$	Pike & Wilson, (1971)	0.333

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Linear Parameter

4.1.1 Stream order- In the Upper Kiul River Basin, total 1235 streams are identified, 971 streams are categorized as 1st order, 208 as 2nd order, 45 as 3rd order, 8 as 4th order, 2 as 5th order, and one as 6th order, as detailed in the Table (2) and the methodology and product are presented in fig. 8 & 9. The abundance of 1st order streams suggests the existence of hilly terrain in the basin area. The Upper Kiul River, a 6th-order basin, reflects higher discharge rates of water, sediment, and nutrients. Stream order increases as stream number decreases, shaped by the physiography.

Figure 8Methodology to produce the drainage network

Figure 9Stream order

4.1.2 Stream number –. The stream networks in the study area exhibit a hierarchical pattern, following Horton’s geometric progression and displaying a nearly linear trend on a logarithmic scale, as illustrated in Fig. 10. In the study area, the dominance of 1st-order streams (78.6%) and 2nd-order streams (16.8%) reflects the region’s rugged, hilly terrain. Table 2 suggests that areas around 4th-order streams offer excellent opportunities for developing reservoirs and water-harvesting systems, which could improve irrigation and soil moisture.

4.1.3 Stream length -The cumulative streams length is 1010.32 kilometres. The lengths of the remaining streams of specific orders are specified in Table (2). 1st order streams are highest in term of total length, and decreases as we progress to higher orders, depicted in the Fig. 11. Higher values suggest a more developed and interconnected network of channels, while lower values indicate areas with less extensive drainage and shorter flow paths. The log graph (Fig. 12) validates this, highlighting the transition of streams from high-altitude regions to flatter, lowland terrains.

In the study area, the **mean stream lengths** range varies from 0.82 to 11.54 (as illustrated in the Figure13and Table 2), it increases with increasing order. However, variations in slope and terrain characteristics, such as high relief and moderately steep slopes, can lead to exceptions.

Table 2 Stream characteristics (in reference to stream order)

STREAM ORDER	NO. OF STREAM	STREAM LENGTH (IN KM) L_u	MEAN STREAM LENGTH (STREAM LENGTH/NO. OF STREAM) L_{um}	MEAN STREAM LENGTH RATIO L_{urm}	STREAM LENGTH USED IN RATIO L_{ur+r}	$L_{urm} * L_{ur+r}$	WEIGHTED STREAM LENGTH RATIO
1	971	527.98	0.5437	0	0	0	2.3165
2	208	251.03	1.2069	2.2195	779.01169	1729.0536	
3	45	108.37	2.4082	1.9954	359.40182	717.1628	
4	8	50.09	6.2611	2.5999	158.46018	411.9762	
5	2	61.31	30.6565	4.8963	111.40216	545.4613	
6	1	11.54	11.5377	0.3764	72.85083	27.4177	
TOTAL	1235	1010.32	0.8181	12.0875	1481.12667	3431.0715	

4.1.4 Stream length ratio- The ratio ranges from 0.38 to 2.22, with higher values indicating a more advanced geomorphic stage. This helps evaluate surface flow discharge and erosion levels (Ikbal et al., 2017; Yadav et al., 2014). A peak observed in the 5th-order stream signifies higher permeability and gentler gradients compared to lower-order streams. Fluctuations in the stream length ratio between consecutive orders, influenced by variations in slope and lithology, indicate a late youth stage of geomorphic development.

The **weighted stream length ratio** value of 2.3165 (as shown in Table 2) indicates relatively longer stream lengths in successive orders, reflecting a well-developed drainage network. This higher value suggests that the basin is in a more advanced geomorphic stage, with streams progressively elongating as their order increases.

4.1.5 Length of main channel - It was measured using GIS tools, and it was 74.64 kilometres. More extended main channels often signify a well-developed drainage system, highlighting the basin's ability to accommodate and discharge water and sediments during runoff.

4.1.6 Rho coefficient -In the study area, the Rho Coefficient is 0.57. This indicates moderate drainage development with reasonable connectivity between streams and tributaries, along with hydrological stability due to a balanced interaction between runoff and infiltration, reflecting moderate groundwater potential.

4.1.7 Bifurcation ratio - In the study, values range from 2 to 5.6, with a value of 2 representing the 6th-order stream in the downstream river basin. This area has a flat surface, porous soil, and soft bedrock, which facilitate infiltration and make it an effective groundwater recharge zone. Conversely, values of 4 or higher (as detailed in Table 3) correspond to hilly terrain with hard rock. In these regions, the steeper slopes reduce the infiltration rate, leading to diminished groundwater recharge.

The “*mean bifurcation ratio (R_{bm})*” is 4.18; it indicates the region is primarily defined by hills and mountains, with the drainage pattern heavily influenced by geological structural activity.

In **Weighted mean bifurcation ratio** represents the hierarchical arrangement of the drainage network. A value of 4.684, being on the higher side, indicates increased complexity in the drainage network, with frequent branching and merging.

Table 3-Stream characteristics (in reference to bifurcation ratio)

STREAM_ORDER	NO. OF STREAM	STREAM LENGTH(IN KM)	BIFURCATION RATIO	MEAN BIFURCATION RATIO	NO OF STREAM USED IN RATIO	BIFURCATION RATIO*NO. OF STREAM USED IN RATIO	WEIGHTED MEAN BIFURCATION RATIO
1	971	527.98	4.67	4.1800	1179	5504	4.6840
2	208	251.03	4.62		253	1169	
3	45	108.37	5.63		53	298	
4	8	50.09	4.00		10	40	
5	2	61.31	2.00		3	6	
6	1	11.54	0		0	0	
TOTAL	1235	1010.32			1498	7017.437	

4.2 Aerial Parameter

4.2.1 Stream frequency (Fs)-The stream frequency in the study area varies between 0.4 and 6, with an overall average of 2.14. Sites with higher values indicate the presence of impermeable rock formations, substantial surface water flow, and steep terrain. In contrast, sites with lower values reflect limited topographic variation, consistent geological structures, and increased water flow in smaller streams.

The overall Fs of the study area, as shown in Fig. 14, reflects a low frequency. This reduces water infiltration, potentially minimizing surface runoff and decreasing the risk of flooding in the basin.

4.2.2 Drainage density (Dd)- The study area was segmented into 5 km × 5 km grids, and a stream network was overlaid onto this grid system. Stream values were computed for each grid, leading to the creation of a drainage density map (Fig. 15).

The study area has a drainage density (Dd) of 1.8 km/km², with values ranging from 0.053 to 3.109 km/km². A low drainage density indicates a low potential for surface flow and high infiltration capacity, depending on precipitation intensity. On the other hand, Grids with high drainage density indicate surface runoff, erosion, and flood risks, emphasizing the need to enhance watershed drainage for water management.

4.2.3 Drainage texture- The drainage texture value of 7.14 (as depicted in Table (1)) indicates a relatively finer drainage texture, suggesting that the area has moderate to steep slopes with significant surface runoff, making it potentially vulnerable to soil erosion. A higher value also highlights the need for water management structures in this area.

4.2.4 Drainage intensity- In the study area D_i varies between 0.166 and 1.39 (as shown in Fig. 16). Lower-end values (0.166) indicate low surface runoff and higher infiltration due to a more permeable surface, which also reduces the potential for soil erosion. In contrast, higher-end values (1.39) signify increased surface runoff, reduced infiltration, and a greater potential for erosion in the study area.

4.2.5 Infiltration number-The infiltration number for the study area is approximately 4, indicating a high value, as shown in Fig. 17. This suggests minimal water infiltration, with a substantial portion of water converting into surface runoff, thereby reducing the potential for groundwater recharge. Within the study area, the infiltration number varies from 0.00012 to 9.612. A higher infiltration number corresponds to decreased infiltration and increased surface runoff, while a lower infiltration number indicates greater infiltration and reduced surface runoff.

4.2.6 Length of overland flow-In the study area, the values of L_g fall within the moderate class, i.e., 0.27 as shown in Fig. 18. It represents that basin possesses moderate relief, flow path, runoff, and moderate water infiltration. Further, it can also be inferred that there are fewer chances of flash floods in this area.

4.2.7 Constant of channel maintenance- The C_m value is 0.264. This indicates that, on average, a surface area of 0.264 square kilometres is required in the basin to generate one linear kilometre of river channel as shown in Fig. 19. The C_m value belongs to the low category, suggesting that structural disturbances have less influence on the study area (Rai et al., 2018). A low C_m value reduces the distance travelled by surface water, causing quick water discharge in areas with limited vegetation cover, transitioning into channel flow (Kumar et al., 2014).

4.2.8 Elongated ratio (ER)- It indicates drainage efficiency. Values range from 0.6 to 1.0, with circular basins (>0.9) draining runoff more efficiently than elongated ones (<0.8) (Odiji et al., 2021; Rai et al., 2018). The study area's ER is 0.708, indicating it falls into the "less elongated" category. The terrain exhibits high relative relief, moderate infiltration capacity, and susceptibility to erosion and sediment load, but its relief limits long-distance sediment transport.

4.2.9 Circulatory ratio - The result of circulatory ratio is 0.238, suggesting a watershed shape that is slightly elongated, resulting in a slow discharge of runoff that exhibits mature topography and supportive dendritic drainage pattern.

Figure 14 Stream Frequency

Figure 15 Drainage density

Figure 16 Drainage Intensity

Figure 17 Infiltration number

Figure 18 Land of overland flow

Figure 19 Constant of channel maintenance

4.2.10 Compactness coefficient- The compactness coefficient (Cc) value of the study area is 2.052, indicating a moderate value. This suggests that the basin has a moderately irregular or elongated shape, which further implies a vulnerability to erosion.

4.2.11 Fitness ratio (Fr)- The Fr value is 0.444, which represents a low fitness ratio. A low fitness ratio value indicates that the river network is less developed relative to the size of the drainage basin. Channel-dominant erosion

and streamlined sediment transport will be observed along the main stream. This also suggests a low water retention capacity within the basin and inefficient channelization of water runoff.

4.2.12 Sinuosity index -It measures the deviation of the river from the shortest distance, with a breakpoint of 1.5. The SI value of the study area is 2.03, suggesting a meandering river pattern with significant lateral erosion and depositional processes.

4.2.13 Form factor-It determines the shape of the basin, with values ranging from zero to one. The study area exhibits an Ff value of 0.39, indicating a semi-circular basin shape due to its lower Ff value. This means it is less compact than a circular basin and has a more gradual sediment transport process. This also suggests that the river's peak discharge will be moderate and sustained for a longer duration.

4.2.14 Shape factor -In the study area, the shape factor (Sf) value is 2.534. $Sf > 1$ is considered to fall under the category of a high shape factor, indicating a long and elongated river basin with a dispersed drainage pattern. Due to this, a longer lag time is observed between rainfall and peak discharge. The elongated nature of the basin reduces the localization of sediment deposition. Additionally, it has been observed that the basin is influenced by topographic constraints with moderate chance of flooding in the area.

4.3 Relief Parameter

4.3.1 Basin relief - The highest point of the study area is 527 meters on the northeastern side, and the lowest point is 21 meters at the river mouth in the northern part (Fig. 20). This indicates a moderate slope, leading to reduced surface flow.

4.3.2 Relief ratio - This helps to determine the relief along the length of a specific basin within the watershed.

The relief ratio (RR) for the study area stands at 0.019, indicating a relatively low value, which suggests that bedrock predominantly characterizes the area. The slower discharge of the basin results in marginally increased infiltration potential, contingent upon the prevailing lithology. Consequently, the area exhibits lower susceptibility to erosion (Singh & Singh, 1997).

4.3.3 Channel gradient- The channel gradient of the study area is 6.78. A high channel gradient promotes vertical erosion, leading to the deepening of the channel. Bank erosion may also occur in such conditions. Intense rainfall can exacerbate the situation by accelerating water movement, potentially resulting in low infiltration rate, low groundwater potential and high flooding chance.

4.3.4 Relative relief- The watershed was divided into 1x1 km grids, and each grid's values were categorized (as shown in Fig. 21). Higher values represent rugged terrain, steep slopes, and elevated landscapes, which influence the infiltration rate and increase erosion potential. Conversely, lower values indicate smoother terrain and less elevated areas, leading to improved infiltration rates and a reduced risk of erosion.

4.3.5 Ruggedness Number-The average Ruggedness Number (Rn) value of the study area is 0.9, indicating moderate level (as shown in Fig. 22). However, the Rn values in the study area vary from high to low. Higher Rn values represent steep and dissected terrains, which contribute to rapid surface runoff, reduced infiltration, and a greater risk of intense erosion. On the other hand, lower Rn values are associated with smoother, less dissected terrains that promote slower runoff, better water recharge potential, and lower erosion risk.

4.3.6 Melton roughness number (MRn)- In our study area, the MRn value stands at 21.914, indicating a mainstream characterized by regular flow without debris.

4.3.7 Gradient ratio - The gradient ratio (GR) in the study area is 9 meters per kilometre (m/km), indicating that if we move one km from the river's mouth to its source, there would be an average difference of 9m in its relief. A higher GR signifies a steeper slope, leading to faster runoff and reduced groundwater potential.

4.3.8 Dissection index -In the study area, the Dissection Index (Di) is 0.477, with values ranging from 0 to 1, where 0 indicates a flat surface, and 1 represents a mountainous terrain. A Di value of 0.477 reflects a moderately dissected landscape (as shown in Fig. 23), suggesting that considerable erosion has already taken place, with limited scope for further erosion.

4.3.9 Topographic wetness index - A mathematical expression helps to understand the basin wetness nature (Odiji et al., 2021). As shown in Fig. 24 the TWI value is low when we move towards the southern side due to high terrain, whereas it increases northward. It aids in identifying suitable sites for water harvesting and delineating floodplains, wetlands, and other pertinent areas.

4.3.10 Hypsometric Integral - The HI value for the study area is 48%, suggesting that the river is in a mature stage transitioning towards the old stage. The curve is almost parallel to the 45-degree line, which signifies the river's gentle erosion potential. Monadnocks may also occur in some areas as shown in Fig. 25.

Figure 25 Hypsometric integral of basin

4.3.11 Asymmetric factor -It refers to the extent of tilt observed in the basin. An AF value below 50 indicates a tilt to the right, whereas a value above 50 indicates a tilt to the left (Bhat et al., 2013). The AF value for the study area is 57%.

4.3.12 Longitudinal profile - In the study area, the longitudinal profile exhibits normal behaviour. No knick-point in the area indicates that there have been no tectonic activities over the geological period (Bhat et al., 2013). The profile of the river also indicates that it is in the mature stage and slowly marching towards the old stage as shown in Fig. 26.

Figure 26 Longitudinal profile

5. Conclusion

With advancements in remote sensing and GIS technology analysing geospatial data has become more manageable. Remote sensing has progressed from optical sensors to RADAR-based data such as ALOS-PALSAR, while GIS has simplified the handling and manipulation of the data set. Morphometric analysis has been identified as an essential study for conducting watershed management studies, where these techniques play a crucial role.

The drainage network of the Upper Kiul River basin demonstrates a semi-dendritic pattern. This study used three main aspects of morphometric analysis and various parameters. The study found that most of the area is characterized by hilly terrain. The relief aspect of morphometric parameters implies a relatively low infiltration rate in the area, resulting in reduced groundwater potential. In the upper section of the basin area, soil erosion occurs due to high river velocity, which facilitates the erosion and transportation of sediments. Conversely, sediment deposition occurs in the lower part where velocity becomes less, particularly in higher-order streams, providing opportunities for good agriculture and groundwater potential in the lower section.

Considering the overall aerial extent of the basin, the values of parameters such as elongated ratio, form factor, circulatory ratio, and others validate the semi-circular to oval nature of the basin, indicating that the river has a moderate susceptibility to flooding. The drainage density of the area indicated that the region is suitable for agriculture, irrigation-based farming, and domestic water supply, thereby enhancing water resource management practices. By examining the stream frequency and drainage texture map, it becomes apparent that coarse spacing

between streams indicates sparse. The river stage is classified as mature to old, signifying that 48% of the study area has undergone erosion, leaving 52%.

The morphometric analysis carried out using remote sensing and GIS-based assessment help in the identification of terrain attributes favorable for the hydrological processes of the basin. Additional studies using satellite-based data synthesized with verified ground-truth data can improve the comprehension levels and further validate the development of watershed management systems. All the findings from this exercise can be utilized in the effective planning and management of the Upper Kiul River basin.

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